

Representation of Women in Literature

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Abstract

The fact that there is no concrete law that forbids women to write doesn't mean that women are completely free to write. It has remained virtually unchanged since time immemorial that, the writings of women are 'mere crap.' This kind of criticism have never stopped women from taking up writing as a passion and profession. Although the women writers are comparatively less acknowledged than the men, they continue to produce various genres of literature. They do it despite a number of hurdles that hinder women. The two major impediments that women face are the financial support and the lack of leisure. The gender roles confined women at home, since they have to take care of the household chores, while men were expected to work and earn the bread. The reversal of gender roles was strictly prohibited and any women who dared to step out of the home became the victim of abuse and criticism. She even became an example of a "Bad Woman." Despite all these social, and economical limitations women continue to write. The main objective of this paper is to scrutinize the women characters created by women in literature. The two main characters chosen for study are: Chandi from a short story title Bayen by Mahasweta Devi and Chetna from the novel Hangwoman by K.R. Meera. These two characters are the victims of double marginalization because they belong to the marginalized gender and community. These two characters represent the women in India who are the victims of marginalization and exploitation. This paper also touches upon the representation and misrepresentation of women by male authors. The paper also focuses on defending the point that, there is an immediate need for the right kind of representation of women in literature and words indeed hold the power to sustainable development.

Keywords: Marginalization, Representation, Victimization, Gender roles, Power.

Introduction

In the biblical tradition, God first created Adam, and “whatsoever Adam called every living creature, that was the name thereof.” The power of words was first given to a man and since then, both writing and appreciation of literature has been dominated by men. Further, literature itself is dominated by male phenomena and it is the male phenomena and their view of life is been considered as right and mature form. Even the women were made to identify themselves through the male point of view. In rare cases, if a woman dares to present her own view, it is dismissed as a “childish view point.”

It is evident from various instances that men were not happy when women started writing literatures. Three reason can be drawn to defend this:

1. Ideological: women were always considered as an inferior sex. Therefore if a woman writes, it indirectly means that anyone can write. This in turn will decrease the value of literature and which is considered to be “a high prestige activity worthy of the efforts of men.” For example, in the motor bike advertisements, a woman actually riding a motorbike implicates that anyone can do it.
2. Psychological: it is inevitable to conceal the reason that many male critics didn't accept and encourage women writers is because, they were scared of the woman's point of view about men.
3. Practical: if a woman starts writing, the daily lifestyle of men will become a chaos. The reason is woman always attends to the household chores. If she choose to write, she had to choose it over her housework. If they choose to be in library, men had to attend the household works.

Therefore the men intellectuals invented various reasons to prevent women from writing. The two practical reason that make women prefer not to write are: lack of leisure and financial dependence. Virginia Woolf in her essay *A Room of One's Own* puts forth the fact that the classics like *Wuthering Heights*, *Jane Eyre*, *Persuasion* were written by women writers who started their literary career with hardly any money. They had to procrastinate their work in order to earn and save money. Women like Jane Austen who propagated about the importance of right kind of marriage; herself was unmarried until her death.

On the other hand women writers like Virginia Woolf and Sylvia Plath, had been married but they made multiple suicide attempts. Virginia Woolf was constantly torn between her personal life and literary career. The reason was they were constantly dependent on either their father or husband.

Despite all these restrictions, some stubborn women do manage to get their works published. Even then they were belittled or hardly acknowledged for their efforts. One of the simplest reason that men usually claim to reject such works is, 'she must have hired some man to write it for her' or 'she must added her name to a work anonymously penned by someone else.' For example there was a popular rumor that works of Charlotte, Anne and Emily Bronte were indeed written by their deceased brother Branwell. This is one reason why women writers including Mary Anne Evans wrote under a male pseudonym as George Eliot.

Feminist Literary Criticism and Gynocriticism

Since time immemorial, there has been a debate to judge the standard of women's writings. Few women literary critics and philosophers including Simone de Beauvoir and Adrienne Rich have always opposed the act of judging women's writings based on the yardsticks and touchstones created by men. Elaine Showalter in her essay, *A literature of their own* insists on creating a separate literary canon exclusively for women. She called upon creating a touchstone with which women's writings should be judged and not with the regulations set by men. She describes three phases of women's writing: the feminine, the feminist and the female stages. In the Feminine Phase, dated 1840- 1880, women concentrated on producing literature that grunted the standards of men. In this phase, the women authors adopted the male pseudonym. This was widely adopted by women writers in England. The writings that were produced in this phase were oblique because the inferiority complex of the female writers was explicit through their writings.

The second phase is the Feminist Phase dated 1882- 1920, and during this period women gained their right to vote. During this phase, women writers expressed their opinions and dramatized the ordeals of wrong womanhood.

The third phase is the Female Phase with is an ongoing since 1920. In this phase, women writers have rejected both imitation and against men and their standard. During this phase, women writers exhibit independent attitudes. They have understood that there is an immediate need to pen down their own opinions and experiences which are obviously different from that of men. They have also realized the importance of creating literature and other forms of art to establish themselves as independent women. In this phase, the contribution of Virginia Woolf and Dorothy Richardson are remarkable. They concentrated writing masculine journalism and feminine fiction. Virginia Woolf even went ahead in framing male and female sentences. They also redefined and sexualized internal and external experiences.

In her essay, Elaine Showalter puts forth that there is no definite theory of feminist literary criticism. Therefore she divides it into two broad categories. The first category is the Feminist Critique, where the woman plays the role of a reader. Here Showalter puts forth the importance of reading. Woman will now have an opportunity to read the literatures produced by men and she will be able to analyze and scrutinize the ways in which men have depicted women and their relations with men. By reading a large variety of books women will be able to identify the stereotyped images of her in the men's writings. This will result in exposing the nature of subjection of women by men and on the other hand women will become conscious of her situation.

The second category of feminist literary criticism is usually referred to as Gynocriticism. It is concerned about woman as a writer and not as a reader. Here the concentration is laid on patterns of women's writings including the narrative technique, the relationship between the writer's lives and their work, appreciation of neglected writers, language and subject matter, and most importantly the construction of a literary tradition that is exclusively women's. The important task of Gynocritics is to give the women writers the same kind of critical attention that a man receives throughout his literary career. This is important because, many women writers are ignored and under-rated because their protagonists are woman characters or because their writing style or theme doesn't fit into the standards laid down by men.

Womanism

The Feminist movement was initially started by the efforts of the middle class white women and the women of color held hardly any significant position in propagating the movement. Beyond that, the feminist movement concentrated on the issues that were faced by the white middle class women especially in the first wave of feminist movement the agenda was to gain suffrage rights for white women. The second wave of feminism concentrated on social and cultural rights including reproductive rights, sexuality, family law and workplace rights. In all these endeavors the equality and justice for Black women were hardly taken into consideration. It is a desolate fact that many feminists were inturn racists. Justine Tally in her article why 'Womanism? The Genesis of a New Word and What It Means, claims that "many early so-called feminists supported racist eugenics initiatives, including sterilization of minority women".

Alice Walker in her book *In Search of Our Mothers' Garden: Womanist Prose* (1983) coined the term Womanist. Womanist, according to Walker, "Womanish, the opposite of girlish...Being grown up...A Black Feminist or Feminist of Color...A woman who loves other women, sexually and/or non-sexually. Appreciates and prefers women's culture, women's emotional flexibility (values tears as natural counterbalance of laughter), and women's strength. Sometimes loves individual men, sexually and/or non-sexually".

It is important to note that women of color or the African American women were suffering from the political and social inequality just like the white women, but they were also oppressed because of their skin color and their ethnicity. These were the important points that were not taken

into consideration by the white feminists. Therefore the women of color were not able to associate themselves with the feminism movement and they deliberately wanted a movement that exclusively represents their cause.

The major difference between Feminism and Womanism is that, some feminists present men as their enemy in their fight for equality against patriarchy. While the Womanism concentrates on gender equality and justice against racial oppression for both African American men and women. Therefore Womanism should not be seen as a movement against Feminism but rather, as Alice Walker quotes, “Womanism is simply another shade of feminism. It helps give visibility to the experience of black women and other women of color who have always been at the forefront of the feminist movement yet marginalized and rendered invisible in historical texts and the media”.

Representation of Women by the Male Writers

Case I: Frailty, thy name is woman.

The play *The Tragedy of Hamlet, Prince of Denmark*, by William Shakespeare provides a picture of women and their role in the Elizabethan England. Although England was ruled a woman, the women were dependent on their male companions. Although the women characters in the play are present in the court and may not represent the common women, the psychological and sexual trauma they undergo is common for all woman. For instance, Ophelia, who is a maiden, had to obey her father without raising any question against him.

Gertrude, the mother of Hamlet who upon her husband’s death, married his brother is been portrayed as a woman who is weak and driven by sexual desire. Feminist critic Carolyn Heilbrun argues that “she is solicitous of Hamlet, asking him to sit near her to give him a sense of belonging to the court, and her speech on Ophelia’s death is a model of decorum and sensitivity.” She also claims that through Gertrude’s speech it is obvious that she is able to see the reality clearly, she even expresses it. She knows that, lust is her sin, and she admits it. She also thinks that her son Hamlet is mad and promises that she will never betray him, and at the end of the play she does not betray him.

Case II: The Marble Vault:

Andrew Marvell’s poem *To His Coy Mistress* pleads for sex using the logical argument that since they have not “world enough, and time” to delay the pleasures, it is important that the couples should proceed with haste. But the poem’s logic and its borrowing from traditional love poetry fails to conceal the psychosexual matters but its shocking attack on the female body.

The woman in this poem is not only unwilling to accept the speaker and that is the reason behind the narrator using metaphysics. The narrator even frightens her into sexual compliance and that is obvious through the violent and grotesque descriptions that make about her body. The woman’s body is compared to a “Marble Vault” and it is an important image that occurs in the center of the poem. He says, if she refuses him, “then worms shall try/ that long preserved virginity.” Written in the context of Renaissance poetic tradition of equaling the female body with a fortress that must be assaulted, and phrased in terms of the seventeenth century’s fondness for morbid and grotesque Metaphysical imagery, the poem powerfully depicts the secondary status of female body.

Representation of Women by the Female Writers

Analysis of Chandi in Bayen

Mahaswetha Devi, being an Indian Bengali socio- political activist and fiction writer has created many powerful women characters who represent millions of women in India. One such powerful character is Chandi from her short story *Bayen*. The word *Bayen* means witch. The story is about the patriarchal family head Malinder, his wife Chandi and their son Bhagirath. They belong to Dom

community. When Bhagirath questions his father about Chandibayen, he recounts the story of his wife, who was once beautiful and is now the bayen. Malinder has secured a job at the sub-divisional morgue only because he knew to sign his name. His wife belongs to Kalu Dom community whose ancestral job is to bury children who had died before reaching the age of five. After her father's death, Chandi has taken up the job of burying the children because she was not afraid of neither dark nor death. One day Chandi was crying when she returned home. She told Malinder that she has been stoned by the people of her own community. Chandi used to go to the grave at night to put bramble on the graves to prevent the wolves from eating the corpses. When the villagers saw her working at night in the graveyard, they named her as Bayen. Chandi even thought of giving up her work, but no one was willing to take up the job after her.

One day, Malinder's niece Tukni contracted chicken pox and eventually died. Her family blamed her for the child's death. On the very same day, Chandi gave up her job. Two months later, the villagers saw Chandi putting bumbles on the grave on a stormy night. They started pelting stones at her and they even cursed her as a Bayen. Malinder, instead of supporting his wife, took side of the villagers. He even went further and announced the village by beating the drum that his wife has now become a Bayen.

The story ends with Chandibayen, saving a train from the robbers and in that process, she loses her life. On receiving the information, the railway authorities, congratulate the brave act of Chandi and they offer money to her family. It is then the villagers accept her as a stellar member of their community and even Malinder who disowned his wife, comes forward and accepts the money.

It is important to note that, the role of Chandi is being mocked by her community. She had no option but to take up the job because she was the only child to her father. Once she is secluded out of the society as a bayen she is forced to follow certain rules. She should live alone at the outskirts of the village. If she ever wishes to enter the village, she had to announce her arrival beforehand. She should not look at men. If she looks at them, she shouldn't look into their face directly but only through a reflective surface. She should not eat too much. She can kill herself, but others are prohibited to kill her. It is also believed that if anybody ill-treats bayen's son, their child will die.

In this short story, Mahaswetha has presented an illiterate society that is patriarchal and superstitious. It is the society that has created the catch-22 situation that engulfed the peaceful and harmonious life of Chandi. A husband during his marriage takes a vow that he will support his wife through all her endeavors but here Malinder goes against the vow and supports the society when he should have supported his wife. Chandi on the other hand has broken the norms of the society but taking up a job that would be continent for a man rather than a woman. Chandi is a woman who is strong and unafraid to enter the graveyard even at a stormy night. It is important to note that, although Chandi is a mother, she continues to bury the dead children. Mahaswetha had taken effort to depict the real psychological trauma that Chandi as a mother underwent while she buried the corpse of the children. The society had inflicted physical, emotional, and psychological wound on a vulnerable woman.

Analysis of Chetna in Hangwoman

The novel focuses about the Grddha Mullick family's culture and profession of executing men who are sentenced to death by the law and this had always been performed by men in the family. Grddha means Vulture in Bengala because the family members possess the bulging eyes similar to those of vultures. The novel is set in Kolkata, and opens with the 88-year old Phanibhushan Grddha Mullick, who is demanding the executing job to be granted to his 22-year old daughter Chetna. Phanibhushan takes pride in the fact that he has executed 451 criminals. Chetna is almost

the last descendants of a Bengali family of executioners, whose grandmother often claims that their family history can be traced even before Christ. Every child born into their family is expected to possess the talent of making the perfect noose by their birth. Chetna's realization that she can make one such perfect noose herself is remarkable. She is a brilliant student. After she completed her school education, she joins in a job, where the owner of the shop tries to assault her sexually. Being born into the family of Mullick, she instantly makes a noose with her dupatta and she held around the neck of the owner. She made him beg to leave him alive although she didn't intend to kill him. When she narrated the incident to her family Phanibhushan was proud that after him, his daughter will take up the family job. Chetna has a brother, who was hacked in the limbs and therefore he doesn't stand a chance to take up the profession.

The novel also focuses on the role of media in shaping a woman's life. Sanjeev Kumar Mitra, the anchor of CNC channel comes with the 'media stunt' claiming that he will be able to secure a government job for Chetna. He conducts a series of interview and debates in his channel and thus make Chetna popular and the issue political. Behind the camera, Mitra begins to manipulate Phanibhushan and tricks him into believing that he is in love with Chetna and will marry her. When Phanibhushan gives his consent that his daughter will marry him, he utilizes all opportunities to assault her sexually. Although Chetna doesn't like it she is torn between men and self-respect. She says, "I lowered my head and remained silent. I alone knew that it was not a matter of courage; it was more of helplessness."

The novel ends with Chetna breaking free from the exploitative lover and her imperious father. She puts up a stellar performance as she conducts her maiden execution and becomes the first and the only hangwoman.

Conclusion

In both these literary works, Chetna and Chandi have taken up a job that is associated with death and men. It is the job that becomes a twist in their life. Chandi is more of a naïve woman who possess the strength of a man, while Chetna is a strong woman who prefers to show herself as naïve. When Chetna says, "I could find no man about whom I could say: this is my god. Everyone demanded worship. Not one could prove he deserved it" it is obvious that, she is a self-righteous woman.

By analyzing these two texts it is evident that, women are not extremes- either too weak or too strong, but their character is a spider's web. It may appear simple, but it is complicated and takes an endless effort to keep it intact. The right kind of representation of woman is mandatory because, the character that writers create are immortal and they represent millions and millions of women who share similar issues. Therefore it is the responsibility of the author to represent women at their right form and should never let their characters fall into extremities and end up creating stereotypes.

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